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WAYS OF INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF THE SERVICE SECTOR IN RURAL AREAS

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Abstract- This article focuses on the importance of the formation and development of an agroservice system in rural areas, which not only creates additional opportunities for agricultural producers to reduce production and transportation costs, increase production efficiency, ensure the financial stability of farms, but also provides employment to the population.

Keywords- Agroservice System, Agriculture, Liberalization Of The Economy, Modernization, Agrarian Sector, Sustainable Development.

I. INTRODUCTION

According to the report “World Inequality 2026”, 75% of the world’s wealth is concentrated in the hands of 10% of the population. Less than 60 thousand people (0.001% of the world’s population) own three times more wealth than the poorest half of the planet’s population. The ongoing research involved 200 scientists. They found that in almost all regions of the world, 1% of the population (the richest people) own more wealth than 90% of the population. It is noted that inequality in the distribution of wealth has grown rapidly in 2025.

“The richest 10% of the world’s population owns 75% of all wealth, while half of humanity owns 2%. As a result, we have a world where a very few have unprecedented financial power, while billions of people remain outside even simple economic stability,” said the authors of the study, led by Ricardo Gomez-Carrera (Paris School of Economics).

The conditions for the liberalization and modernization of our country’s economy create the need to increase and develop agroservice entities that provide various services to agricultural enterprises, farmers and peasant farms, and provide them with various services to ensure the systematic and continuous development of the agricultural sector.

Especially in the context of the rapid formation of market economic relations in our country, it is necessary to scientifically study the institutional foundations of the formation and development of the agroservice market in our republic, the stages of transition to market relations, and the organizational and economic mechanisms for state support of this market.

It is also necessary to pay special attention to economic relations, which are considered very important in the agroservice economy today, in particular, to the analysis and specific features of the system of economic relations between

agroservice entities and their agricultural enterprises, as well as their economic relations in improving the mechanism for financing agroservice and providing credit resources.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

According to Professor M.Muhammedov, “The poor population can be divided into two categories. The first category is those who do not want to improve their lives, and even if they want to, they are too lazy to try. The second category is people who have become like this for certain reasons, who want to work, but for some reason cannot do so.”

According to Professors M.Pardaev and O.Pardaev, “The population falling into the poverty category can be divided into three groups. The first is the unemployed, people who have the appropriate qualifications but cannot find a suitable job. The second category is people who are employed but their monthly salary is not enough to lift their families out of poverty. The third is the population that does not have the opportunity to work (disabled, incapable, children and the elderly without a breadwinner).”

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This article focuses on the issues of poverty reduction in the context of the development of New Uzbekistan, by studying the problems existing in each family. The methods of identification, analysis, synthesis, systematic analysis, and observation-questionnaire were used to study the issues of poverty reduction.

IV. ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In each direction of the economic reforms being implemented in our republic, along with the development of the activities of agricultural producers, great attention is paid to the further formation and development of agroservice structures serving farmers and peasant farms, as well as their support by the state. Because it is appropriate to recognize that the formation and development of an agroservice system in rural areas is a particularly noteworthy issue, as it creates additional opportunities for agricultural producers to reduce the costs of growing and transporting products, increase production efficiency, and ensure the financial stability of farms, both directly and indirectly. In addition, the increase and development of agroservice entities in rural areas also allows reducing the social tension of agrarian reforms, as it opens up ways to attract part of the population to labor activities not directly related to agriculture.

In the development of agroservice services in our country, the rapid development of the agricultural agroservice service system is of great importance. Firstly, there is an increase in financial resources in agricultural agroservice entities or an increase in investor interest in this sector, and secondly, there is a need to ensure stable and high growth rates of the agroservice service system on the basis of public-private partnership.

Today, 45.3 percent of the world's population lives in rural areas. According to data, "70 percent of the world's total poor population also live in rural areas." This requires further strengthening the objective need to study the problems of creating new jobs and increasing incomes in the service sector. Therefore, comprehensive research into the service sector, highlighting its essence and specific economic aspects, revealing its role and significance in the modern economy, and most importantly, increasing attention to the problems of increasing the efficiency of the service sector in rural areas are urgent tasks.

Table 1

Share of the service sector in urban and rural areas in selected countries (as a percentage of the total) 2023

No.	Countries	Share of the service sector (%)	
		City	Village
1	India	85.0	15.0
2	Germany	72.4	27.6
3	Uzbekistan	86.8	13.2
4	In the world	80.4	19.6

Table 1 shows that in India, the service sector lags behind urban areas by almost 6 times in rural areas, 2.6 times in Germany, 6.0 times in Uzbekistan, and 4.1 times globally. This means that rural residents consume 4.3 times less services than urban areas. According to the results of the analysis, the proper organization of agro-service services in rural areas, on the one hand, provides employment for the population, and on the other hand, solves poverty.

As can be seen from the data, the provision of stable and high economic growth rates in our republic made it possible to reduce the poverty rate from 23 percent in 2019 to 11 percent in 2023.

The goal was to take measures to improve the living conditions of the population, develop entrepreneurship, reduce poverty, and achieve the effectiveness of social support programs in the regions of our country using a new approach and the application of accumulated national experience to a higher level. These measures include:

1. Ensuring high-income, stable employment of the population, creating conditions for youth to receive education and vocational training based on innovative and digital technologies, access to medical and social services for all segments of society, and implementing comprehensive measures to develop the infrastructure of neighborhoods, thereby lifting 500 thousand people out of poverty in the remaining period of 2024 and 1 million in 2025;

2. Based on the positive results achieved in the field of poverty reduction by the Ministry of Poverty Reduction and Employment, the Ministry of Economy and Finance, and the National Agency for Social Protection, and on the basis of accumulated national experience and best international practices, the tasks of

implementing the “From Poverty to Prosperity” program have been set, which encourages every citizen to take a responsible approach to the future of himself and his children and creates opportunities for them to realize their potential.

Table 2**Changes in the volume of services per capita in Uzbekistan**

No.	Years	Volume of services per capita (in million soums)	From this		in services per capita of rural population compared to urban population , million soums (+;-)
			Volume of services per capita of urban residents, million soums	Volume of services per capita of rural population, million soums	
1	2016	2.8	4.6	1.0	- 3.6
2	2017	3.6	5.2	1.2	-4.0
3	2018	4.1	7.5	1.4	-6.1
4	2019	5.8	9.7	1.8	-7.9
5	2020	6.4	10.6	2.0	-8.6
6	2021	8.1	13.5	2.3	-11.2
7	2022	9.9	16.8	2.7	-14.1
8	2023	12.9	21.7	3.4	-18.3

The volume of services per capita in the Republic of Uzbekistan amounted to 12.9 million soums in 2023, which is a 4.6-fold increase compared to 2016. In cities, the volume of services per capita in 2023 amounted to 21.7 million soums, and in rural areas - 3.4 million soums, that is, an increase of 4.7 times in cities and 2.4 times in rural areas compared to 2016. The volume of services per capita in rural areas is 18.3 million soums less than the volume of services per capita in urban areas (Table 1). If we take into account that almost 50 percent of the permanent population lives in rural areas, we are convinced that it is necessary to rapidly develop the service sector in rural areas. In rural areas, the volume of services per capita tends to decrease compared to urban areas. In urban areas, the volume of services per capita tends to increase relatively rapidly compared to rural areas.

V. CONCLUSION/RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the analysis we have in assessing the role of the service sector in improving the living standards of the population and providing employment in rural areas, the number of jobs in this sector is of great importance. However, we studied not in terms of how many jobs there are in the service sector, but rather in terms of the factors that positively affect poverty reduction by continuously providing the population with existing jobs in the service sector. Each new job created in the service sector, along with providing employment, leads to a decrease in the poverty levels of the population.

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